

Antiviral and antibacterial secondary metabolites from Thai invertebrate-associated fungi

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Abbreviations

¹ H	hydrogen atom, proton
BGC	conserved biosynthetic gene cluster
CD	circular dichroism
CHIKV	Chikungunya virus
CPRO	Compound Profiling and Screening
COSY	correlated spectroscopy
DMSO	dimethyl sulfoxide
ESI-MS	electrospray ionization mass spectrometry
ESI-TOF-MS	electrospray ionization time-of-flight mass
GG1	glucose glycerol
HMBC	heteronuclear multiple bond correlation
HPLC	high performance liquid chromatography
HR-ESI-MS	high-resolution electrospray ionization mass spectrometry
HRMS	high-resolution mass spectrometry
HSQC	heteronuclear single quantum coherence
IC ₅₀	half-maximal inhibitory concentration
LC-MS	liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry
MIC	minimal inhibitory concentration
Min	minutes
MAA	microporenic acid
MYC	mycosel agar
MS/MS	tandem mass spectrometry

MTPA	α -methoxy- α -trifluoromethylphenylacetyl-chloride
NMR	nuclear magnetic resonance
NPs	natural products
PDA	potato dextrose agar
PDB	potato dextrose broth
PKS	polyketide synthase
PKS-NRPS	polyketide synthase-nonribosomal peptide synthetase
ROESY	rotating frame Overhauser enhancement spectroscopy
UV	ultraviolet
Vis	visible
YM	yeast malt extract

Abstract

The aim of this thesis is to investigate the secondary metabolites obtained from diverse invertebrate-associated fungi, with the main goal of exploring their bioactivity and structural diversity. This investigation includes studying three different Thai species from the ascomycete order Hypocreales: *Cordyceps javanica*, and two recently described species, *Beauveria neobassiana* and *Samsoniella aurantia*. In a preliminary medium-throughput screening, the total extracts from the above-mentioned strains exhibited promising antiviral properties against the Chikungunya virus (CHIKV) and were selected for the characterization of their secondary metabolites.

From the different evaluated media, the cultivation of *C. javanica* in glucose glycerol (GG1), *B. neobassiana* in yeast malt extract (YM), and *S. aurantia* in rice solid medium had positive impacts on the production of diverse secondary metabolites. After preparative purification of the total extracts obtained from the scaled-up cultivation in the aforementioned media, a total of eight compounds (**1-8**) were isolated from *C. javanica*, four of which (**1,3,6,8**) were previously undescribed. From *B. neobassiana*, seven compounds (**9-15**) were isolated and elucidated, whereas six compounds (**16-21**) were obtained and identified from *S. aurantia* with three previously undescribed compounds from the total extracts of both strains. Extensive analysis, including liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS), high-resolution electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (HR-ESI-MS), and 1D and 2D nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, helped identify these compounds. The obtained results revealed that *C. javanica* produced a class of cyclodepsipeptides trivially named beauverolides (**1-8**). In parallel, the metabolomics analyses highlighted the structural diversity of these metabolites. Moreover, they played a key role in confirming structural hypotheses and exploring non-isolated compounds. *Beauveria neobassiana* produced several polyketide synthase-nonribosomal peptide synthetase (PKS-NRPS)-derived metabolites, including vancouverone C (**9**), pyridovericin (**10**), 15-OH-tenellin (**11**), prototenellin D (**12**), vancouverone D (**13**), pretenellin B (**14**) and tenellin (**15**). Notably, prototenellin D (**12**) emerged as a promising anti-biofilm agent against *Staphylococcus aureus* biofilms, characterized by the absence of antimicrobial activity and low cytotoxicity against the tested microorganisms and cell lines, respectively. Similarly, tenellin (**15**) showed notable potential against *Bacillus subtilis*.

Samsoniella aurantia was found to produce 2-pyridones (**16**, **17**, **19**) along with two additional beauvericin derivatives (**18**, **21**) and simplicilliumtide E (**20**). These findings include the novel farinosone D (**16**).

The initial findings suggested potential antiviral effects; however, due to the absence of accessible test data, we shifted our focus to investigating the extracts for potential bioactive compounds. Nevertheless, our research not only provided us with an in-depth understanding of the different structural entities and bioactivities of secondary metabolites derived from Thai invertebrate-associated fungi, but it also enhanced our understanding of natural products and their various applications, especially against infectious diseases.

Zusammenfassung

Ziel dieser Arbeit ist die Untersuchung der Sekundärmetaboliten verschiedener wirbellose-assoziierten Pilze mit dem Hauptziel, ihre Bioaktivität und strukturelle Vielfalt zu erforschen. Diese Untersuchung umfasst die Erforschung von drei verschiedenen thailändischen Arten aus der Ascomycetenordnung Hypocreales: *Cordyceps javanica* und zwei kürzlich beschriebene Arten, *Beauveria neobassiana* und *Samsoniella aurantia*. In einem vorläufigen Mitteldurchsatz-Screening wiesen die Gesamtextrakte der oben genannten Stämme vielversprechende antivirale Eigenschaften gegen das Chikungunya-Virus (CHIKV) auf und wurden für die Charakterisierung ihrer Sekundärmetaboliten ausgewählt.

Von den verschiedenen bewerteten Medien hatten die Kultivierung von *C. javanica* in Glukose-Glycerin (GG1), *B. neobassiana* in Hefe-Malzextrakt (YM) und *S. aurantia* in festem Reismedium positive Auswirkungen auf die Produktion verschiedener Sekundärmetaboliten. Nach der präparativen Aufreinigung der Gesamtextrakte, die bei der Kultivierung in den oben genannten Medien gewonnen wurden, konnten insgesamt acht Verbindungen (**1-8**) aus *C. javanica* isoliert werden, von denen vier (**1,3,6,8**) bisher unbeschrieben waren. Aus *B. neobassiana* wurden sieben Verbindungen (**9-15**) isoliert und aufgeklärt, während sechs Verbindungen (**16-21**) aus *S. aurantia* gewonnen und identifiziert wurden, darunter drei bisher unbeschriebene Verbindungen aus den Gesamtextrakten beider Stämme. Umfangreiche Analysen, einschließlich Flüssigchromatographie-Massenspektrometrie (LC-MS), hochauflösende Elektrospray-Ionisations-Massenspektrometrie (HR-ESI-MS) sowie 1D- und 2D-Kernresonanzspektroskopie (NMR), halfen bei der Identifizierung dieser Verbindungen. Die erzielten Ergebnisse zeigten, dass *C. javanica* eine Klasse von Cyclodepsipeptiden produziert, die Beauverolide (**1-8**) genannt werden. Parallel dazu machten die Metabolomanalysen die strukturelle Vielfalt dieser Metaboliten deutlich. Darüber hinaus spielten sie eine Schlüsselrolle bei der Bestätigung von Strukturhypothesen und der Erforschung nicht isolierter Verbindungen. *Beauveria neobassiana* produzierte mehrere von der Polyketidsynthese und nichtribosomalen Peptidsynthetase (PKS-NRPS) abgeleitete Metaboliten, darunter Vancouveron C (**9**), Pyridovericin (**10**), 15-OH-Tenellin (**11**), Prototenellin D (**12**), Vancouveron D (**13**), Pretenellin B (**14**) und Tenellin (**15**). Insbesondere Prototenellin D (**12**) erwies sich als vielversprechender Anti-Biofilm-Wirkstoff gegen *Staphylococcus aureus*-Biofilme, der sich durch das Fehlen einer antimikrobiellen Aktivität und eine geringe Zytotoxizität gegenüber den getesteten Mikroorganismen bzw. Zelllinien

auszeichnete. In ähnlicher Weise zeigte Tenellin (**15**) ein beachtliches Potenzial gegen *Bacillus subtilis*.

Wir haben festgestellt, dass *S. aurantia* 2-Pyridone (16, 17, 19) sowie zwei weitere Beauvericin-Derivate (18, 21) und Simplicilliumtid E (20) produziert. Zu diesen Ergebnissen gehört auch das neuartige Farinoson D (**16**).

Die anfänglichen Ergebnisse deuteten auf mögliche antivirale Wirkungen hin; da jedoch keine zugänglichen Testdaten vorlagen, verlagerten wir unseren Schwerpunkt auf die Untersuchung der Extrakte auf mögliche bioaktive Verbindungen. Nichtsdestotrotz hat uns unsere Forschung nicht nur ein tieferes Verständnis der verschiedenen strukturellen Einheiten und der Bioaktivität von Sekundärmetaboliten aus thailändischen wirbellose-assozierte Pilzen vermittelt, sondern auch unser Verständnis von Naturstoffen und ihren verschiedenen Anwendungen, insbesondere gegen Infektionskrankheiten, verbessert.

1 Introduction

Natural products (NPs) are widely known for being a rich source of bioactive molecules that hold tremendous potential for the discovery and development of new drugs (Mapook et al. 2022). In recent years, NPs have received more attention as a potential source of new drugs due to their outstanding chemical diversity and distinctive biological activities (Shinde et al. 2019). These various therapeutic possibilities highlight the NPs' enormous potential, spanning across a spectrum of diseases (Atanasov et al. 2021). Counting among their many natural sources, fungi have distinguished themselves as prolific producers of secondary metabolites with a wide range of biological activities, including those having anti-infective properties (Niego et al. 2023).

Natural products derived from fungi have great potential for preventing the growth of pathogenic microorganisms (Atanasov et al. 2021). Many significant anti-infective agents, including penicillins and cephalosporins, have been isolated from fungi. These and other bioactive substances have significantly contributed to medicine and been beneficial in the treatment of a number of infectious diseases. Having a variety of modes of action enables them to treat a wide range of bacterial infections, making them indispensable tools in modern medicine. In fact, the combined sales of these fungal-derived antibiotics exceeded a startling 25 billion US dollars in 2021 and 2022, demonstrating their profound impact on the pharmaceutical sector (Niego et al. 2023). This highlights the profound relevance and effectiveness of fungi in the ongoing fight against infectious diseases.

Entomopathogenic fungi, a subgroup within the broader category of invertebrate-associated fungi, are essential to both medicine and ecology. They have attracted interest in agriculture as safer alternatives to chemical insecticides for pest control. The capacity of entomopathogenic fungi to target certain insect species while being harmless to non-target organisms and the environment added momentum to the use of these organisms as biopesticides. Moreover, these fungi also support nutrient cycling and breakdown in ecosystems, affecting soil health and ecosystem dynamics in general (Mantzoukas et al. 2022). In addition to their ecological importance, they are important sources of diverse secondary metabolites with potential medicinal uses, such as anti-infective substances that have activity against a variety of pathogens. *Beauveria* spp., for instance, have been revealed to produce cytotoxic and antimicrobial compounds, including beauvericins, beauveriolides, and beauverols (Kobmoo et al. 2021). Similar to the above, cordycepin, a substance isolated from *Cordyceps militaris*,

exhibits strong growth-inhibiting effect against *Clostridium* spp. without adversely affecting the growth of beneficial bacteria (Ahn et al. 2000).

In light of various health issues due to its enormous influence on public health, the urgent need for a cure for the Chikungunya virus (CHIKV) has grown ever more evident. A debilitating illness caused by the mosquito-borne infection CHIKV is marked by joint pain and fever. The virus has caused multiple outbreaks in various regions of the world since it made a comeback in the twenty-first century, resulting in significant morbidity and financial burden (Weaver and Lecuit 2015). There are currently no specific antiviral drugs or vaccines that have been licensed for clinical use, despite the fact that CHIKV infections are becoming more common and impactful. The development of effective antiviral agents against this virus using conventional drug development methods, such as high-throughput screening of chemical libraries, has yielded limited success (Kaur et al. 2013). Therefore, the goal of our research is to find potential sources of NPs with fungal origin that could serve as antiviral agents against CHIKV, which served as inspiration for starting the AntiViralFun-Project. In this project, 1082 extracts obtained from wood-inhibiting saprotrophs, aquatic, and entomopathogenic fungi were examined regarding their cytotoxicity and antiviral efficacy against CHIKV. Twenty of these extracts have proven to have promising properties in regard to low cytotoxicity and high antiviral activity. Because comprehensive antiviral assay results for these extracts were not available, our investigation shifted to a broad exploration of the compounds present.

In our study, we focused on three strains, namely *C. javanica*, *B. neobassiana*, and *Samsoniella aurantia*, that were used to generate extracts from the top twenty hits. Those three examined species belong to the order Hypocreales and the family Cordycipitaceae (Helaly et al. 2019; Kobmoo et al. 2021; Mongkolsamrit et al. 2018). *Samsoniella* is a recently introduced genus described in 2018 by Mongkolsamrit et al. Based on morphological and molecular evidence, it differentiates itself from the genus *Akanthomyces*. While both *Cordyceps* and *Samsoniella* have *Isaria*-like forms with white to cream spore-generating structures on insect larvae or pupae, *Samsoniella* spp. differentiate themselves by developing orange synnemata from the host. *Cordyceps* with *Isaria*-like structures are distinguished by conidiogenous cells with a circular or swelling bottom that narrows into a visible neck.

The immense chemical variety of fungal secondary metabolites has largely gone untapped despite notable developments in the field of natural product chemistry. This thesis aims to perform a thorough analysis of secondary metabolites derived from fungi associated with

invertebrates from Thailand. We aim to isolate and elucidate the chemical structures of these bioactive compounds using cutting-edge analytical techniques, such as hyphenated preparative high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, and high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS). Additionally, the finding of bioactive substances in invertebrate-associated fungi may open up new avenues for the creation of next-generation anti-infectives and enhance the field of drug discovery from natural sources.

Figure 1. Photographs of Entomopathogenic Fungi made by Artit Khonsanit– *C. javanica* (a), *B. neobassiana* (b), *S. aurantia* (c)

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

2.1.1 Instruments

Table 1. General devices and appliances

Device	Model	Manufacturer
Autoclave	VX-150	Systec GmbH & Co. KG.; Asbach, Germany
CD spectrometer	J-815	Jasco Deutschland GmbH; Pfungstadt, Germany
Centrifuge	Rotofix 32A	Hettich; Kirchlegern, Germany
Diabetes test strips	Medi-Test for glucose	Machery-Nagel; Düren, Germany
Magnetic stirrer	RCT digital	IKA-Werke; Staufen im Breisgau, Germany
Micropipette	0.5-10 µl, 10-100 µl, 20-200 µl, 100-1000 µl	Eppendorf Vertrieb Deutschland GmbH; Wesseling-Berzdorf, Germany
Nitrogen evaporator	ECHM-12-32	Gebr. Liebisch GmbH & Co. KG; Bielefeld, Germany
NMR spectrometer	Bruker Avance III 700 (¹ H 700 MHz, ¹³ C 175 MHz) Bruker Avance III 500 (¹ H 500 MHz, ¹³ C 125 MHz)	Bruker Daltonik GmbH; Bremen, Germany
Parafilm	Parafilm M All-Purpose Laboratory Film	Bemis Company, Inc.; Neenah, USA
pH meter	InoLab pH 7110	Xylem Analytics Germany Sales GmbH & Co. KG; Weilheim in Oberbayern, Germany
Pipette tips	Ep T.I.P.S. LoRetentionReloads	Eppendorf Vertrieb Deutschland GmbH; Wesseling-Berzdorf, Germany
Polarimeter	MCP 150	Anton Paar Group AG; Graz, Austria
Precision scale	Cubis® MCA225P-2S00-U	Sartorius Lab Instruments GmbH & Co. KG.; Göttingen, Germany
Pumping unit	PC 3001 VARIO select	Vacuubrand GmbH & Co. KG; Wertheim, Germany
Rotary evaporator	Hei-VAP precision	Heidolph Instruments GmbH & Co. KG; Schwabach, Germany
SpeedVac Vacuum pump	RVC 2-25 CD plus CT 02-50 SR	CHRIST®; Osterode am Harz, Germany
Shaker incubator	AG15	Infors HT; Bottmingen, Switzerland
Ultrapure water system	Milli-Q Direct	Merck Chemicals GmbH; Darmstadt, Germany
Ultrasonic bath	Sonorex Digital 10P	Bandelin electronic GmbH & Co. KG; Berlin, Germany
Ultrasonic bath	Sonorex TK52	Bandelin electronic GmbH & Co. KG; Berlin, Germany
UV/Vis Spectrophotometer	UV-2450	Shimadzu Corporation; Kyōto, Japan

Table 2. Devices for purification and analysis

Device	Model	Manufacturer
ESI-IT mass spectrometer	AmaZon speed™	Bruker Daltonics GmbH & Co. KG; Bremen, Germany
Flash chromatography system	Reveleris® X2	W. R. Grace & Co. Columbia; MD, USA
HR-ESI mass spectrometer	MaXis	Bruker Daltonics GmbH & Co. KG; Bremen, Germany

Preparative HPLC system	Gilson PLC 2250	Gilson, Inc.; Middleton; WI, USA
Preparative HPLC system	Büchi Pure C-850 FlashPrep	Büchi Labortechnik GmbH; Essen, Germany
Semipreparative HPLC system	Agilent 1200 Infinity Series	Agilent Technologies Deutschland GmbH; Böblingen, Germany

2.1.2 Chemicals

Table 3. Chemical solvents

Chemical	Manufacturer
Acetone-<i>d</i>₆	J.T. Baker, Avantor Performance Materials; PA, USA
Acetonitrile	J.T. Baker, Avantor Performance Materials; PA, USA
Chloroform-<i>d</i>₆	Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany
Dichloromethane	J.T. Baker, Avantor Performance Materials; PA, USA
Dimethyl sulfoxide	J.T. Baker, Avantor Performance Materials; PA, USA
Dimethyl sulfoxide- <i>d</i> ₆ (DMSO- <i>d</i> ₆)	Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany
Ethyl acetate	J.T. Baker, Avantor Performance Materials; PA, USA
Formic acid	Honeywell Fluka; Seelze, Germany
Heptane	Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany
Methanol	J.T. Baker, Avantor Performance Materials; PA, USA
Methanol, Uvasol®	Supelco Inc., MZ-Analysentechnik GmbH; Mainz, Germany
Methanol-<i>d</i>₄	Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH; Steinheim am Albuch, Germany
(<i>S</i>)-(+)- α -Methoxy- α -trifluoromethylphenylacetylchloride	Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH; Steinheim am Albuch, Germany
(<i>R</i>)-(-)- α -Methoxy- α -trifluoromethylphenylacetylchloride	Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH; Steinheim am Albuch, Germany
Pyridine-<i>d</i>₅	Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany
Ultra-pure water	Milli-Q, Lab Water, Merck Chemicals GmbH; Darmstadt

2.1.3 Media

Table 4. Culture media

Medium	Components	Weight (g/L)	Manufacturer	Type	pH
YM 6.3	Malt extract	10	Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.; MA, USA	Liquid	6.3
	D-Glucose	4	Cerestar Deutschland GmbH; Krefeld, Germany		
	Yeast extract	4	Ohly GmbH; Hamburg, Germany		
ZM ½	Molasses	5	Nordzucker AG; Braunschweig, Germany	Liquid	7.2
	Oatmeal	5	Herrnmühle; Reichelsheim, Germany		
	Sucrose	4	Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany		
	Mannitol	4	AppliChem GmbH; Darmstadt, Germany		

	D-Glucose	1.5	Cerestar Deutschland Gmbh; Krefeld, Germany		
	CaCO ₃	1.5	Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany		
	Edamine	0.5	Thermo Fisher Scientific Oxoid Ltd		
	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	0.5	Merck KGaA; Darmstadt, Germany		
Q6 ½	D-glucose	2.5	Cerestar Deutschland Gmbh; Krefeld, Germany	Liquid	7.2
	Glycerin	10	Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany		
	Cotton seed flour	5	Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH; Steinheim am Albuch, Germany		
MMK2	Mannitol	40	AppliChem GmbH; Darmstadt, Germany	Liquid	-
	Yeast extract	5	Ohly GmbH; Hamburg, Germany		
	Murashige & Skoog salts	4.3	Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH; Steinheim am Albuch, Germany		
BRFT (small)	Yeast extract	1	Ohly GmbH; Hamburg, Germany	Solid	-
	Sodium tartrate	0.5	Merck KGaA; Darmstadt, Germany		
	K ₂ HPO ₄	0.5	Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany		
	Brown rice	280	Davert GmbH; Ascheberg, Germany		
V+YES	Sucrose	150	Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany	Solid	-
	Yeast extract	20	Ohly GmbH; Hamburg, Germany		
	MgSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	0.5	Merck KGaA; Darmstadt, Germany		
	ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	0.0001	MP Biomedicals Germany GmbH; Eschwege, Germany		
	CuSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	0.001	Merck KGaA; Darmstadt, Germany		
	Vermiculite	188	AppliChem GmbH; Darmstadt, Germany		
Supermalt	Malt extract	50	Organotechnie; La Courneuve, France	Liquid	-
	Yeast extract	10	Ohly GmbH; Hamburg, Germany		
	ZnSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	0.007	MP Biomedicals Germany GmbH; Eschwege, Germany		
	FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	0.02	Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany		
GG1	Glycerol	75	Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany	Liquid	7.5
	D-Glucose	10	Cerestar Deutschland Gmbh; Krefeld, Germany		
	Yeast autolysate	5	Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH; Steinheim, Germany		
	Soybean meal	5	W. Schoenenberger GmbH & Co. KG; Magstadt, Germany		
	Tomato paste	5	Hengstenberg; Esslingen, Germany		
	Sodium citrate	2	Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH		
	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	2	Merck KGaA; Darmstadt, Germany		
SMYA	Maltose	42	Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany	Semi-solid	
	Yeast extract	10	Ohly GmbH; Hamburg, Germany		
	Meat peptone	10	Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG; Karlsruhe, Germany		
	Agar (Bacto)	4	Becton, Dickinson and Company; Sparks, USA		

2.1.4 Organisms

Table 5. Fungal strains

Strain No.	Species	Isolation source	Isolation region	Reference
MY11508	<i>Cordyceps javanica</i>	Spiders	Central and Northeastern Thailand	Helaly et al. 2019
MY03181	<i>Beauveria neobassiana</i>	Adult cicada (Hemiptera)	Nakhon Ratchasima Province, Pak Chong District, Khao Yai National Park, Thailand	Kobmoo et al. 2021
MY07955	<i>Samsoniella aurantia</i>	Lepidopteran larva	Kanlayaniwatthana District of Chiang Mai Province, Thailand	Mongkolsamrit et al. 2018

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Screening of *C. javanica* in different culture media

Initially, a small-scale screening process was used to assess *C. javanica* in order to chemically describe the production of secondary metabolites. In this procedure, the fungus was grown in eight different media, consisting of six liquid (YM 6.3, ZM 1.2, Q6 1.1, Supermalt, and MMK2) and two solid ones (rice and vermiculite).

2.2.1.1 Preparation of pre-culture

After *C. javanica* had grown sufficiently on yeast malt extract (YM) 6.3 agar, small pieces were cut using a cork borer with a diameter of 0.5 mm. Five of these pieces were then put into 100 mL autoclaved Erlenmeyer flasks with 50 mL of the semi-solid medium SMYA that had already been prepared. After that, the flasks were incubated for 7 days at 23 °C and 140 rpm. These cultures were then used as pre-culture for the different main cultures.

2.2.1.2 Preparation of main cultures

To prepare the solid media, 28 g of rice or 18.8 g of vermiculite were weighed out and put into 500 mL Erlenmeyer flasks. The liquid BRFT medium was then prepared and 100 mL were added to the rice, just as 50 mL of YES medium were added to the vermiculite. After autoclaving and cooling, 3 mL of the pre-culture were transferred into each flask. Finally, the cultures were incubated for 15 days at 23°C.

500 mL shake flasks were utilized for the liquid cultivation, each containing 200 mL of the respective medium. Hence, 6 mL of the pre-culture were added to each flask. The main cultures were incubated at 23°C and 220 rpm.

2.2.2 Extraction of the secondary metabolites

2.2.2.1 Extraction of secondary metabolites from liquid media

After inoculation, the glucose levels in liquid cultures were regularly measured using Medi-Test glucose strips. Harvesting and extraction of the cultures took place three days after glucose depletion. To separate the supernatant from the mycelium, vacuum filtration was used. Both the supernatant and mycelia were then extracted separately.

The supernatant was submitted to a liquid-liquid extraction twice using ethyl acetate (ratio of 1:1). The resulting organic phase was separated, combined, dehydrated by filtering through anhydrous sodium sulfate, and evaporated under vacuum, while the water phase was discarded. The dried extracts were then transferred into 4 mL vials.

To increase the yield of the total extract, the mycelia were soaked in acetone and subjected to two rounds of ultrasonic bathing for 30 minutes at 40°C. This process enabled the release of compounds present within the mycelia. Following each cycle of ultrasonication, the resultant suspensions were filtered to eliminate any remaining solids, and the liquid was then collected in a round-bottom flask. Meanwhile, the mycelia were soaked in fresh acetone to ensure thorough extraction. Subsequently, the liquid phases of both repetitions were combined, and the acetone evaporated under a vacuum at 40°C to produce a semi-solid residue that was then dispersed in 100 mL of water and subjected to liquid-liquid extraction against ethyl acetate as previously described for the supernatant.

2.2.2.2 Extraction of secondary metabolites from solid media

After 15 days of cultivation at a temperature of 23 °C, the solid media employed in the study were extracted. The extraction procedure for the solid media was similar to the extraction of the mycelia resulting from the liquid media fermentation described in Section 2.2.2.1. The obtained dried total extracts were then diluted in an appropriate volume of methanol. This solution was further exposed to extraction using heptane in a 1:1 ratio. The resulting heptane phase was transferred to a round-bottom flask after being enhanced with nonpolar substances such as fatty acids. The extraction process was crucial in separating the polar compounds still present in the methanol phase from the nonpolar ones.

Following the extraction steps, the contents of both round-bottom flasks were thoroughly dried, and the residues were then transferred into 4 mL vials.

2.2.3 Large-scale cultivation and purification of pure compounds of *C. javanica* in GG1-medium

2.2.3.1 Large-scale fermentation

When compared to the other media, the fungal extracts produced by *C. javanica* in glucose glycerol (GG1) medium displayed a higher production yield of secondary metabolites. Therefore, a scale-up cultivation in the aforementioned medium was done to isolate and identify those metabolites. Both the cultivation process (using 4 L of medium in total with 200 mL per flask) and the extraction steps were identical to those detailed in sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2.1, respectively. The mycelia and the supernatant of all flasks were added together and extracted. Liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) analyses were conducted on both extracts.

2.2.3.2 Liquid-Liquid pre-separation

After ensuring that there were no significant differences in LC-MS profiles between the mycelial and supernatant extracts, they were combined to produce 20 g of total extract. Heptane, methanol, and water were used to perform an initial liquid-liquid pre-separation. Phase separation was facilitated by preparing a 9:1 methanol-to-water solution, which was then combined with an equal volume of heptane in a separatory funnel. Two distinct phases were observed, with a noticeable precipitate present in the methanol-water phase. The precipitate was rigorously filtered using filter paper, resulting in Fraction I. The methanol phase was represented by Fraction II, and the heptane phase by Fraction III. Fractions I (6.0 g), II (12.8 g), and III (1.4 g) were collected in round flasks, evaporated, and stored.

2.2.3.3 Isolation of compounds 1-6 from Fraction I (precipitant)

The purification of the precipitant (6.0g) acquired from the large-scale fermentation was carried out using preparative HPLC using separation conditions detailed in Tables 6 and 7. A total of six compounds, compound **1** (1.2 mg, t_R = 35 min), **2** (5.3 mg, t_R = 42 min), **3** (3.2 mg, t_R = 45 min), **4** (14.1 mg, t_R = 47 min), **5** (6.3 mg, t_R = 56 min) and **6** (0.7 mg, t_R = 54 min) were obtained from sub-fractions 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 9, respectively.

Table 6. Parameter for purification of Fraction I

Parameter	Description
HPLC-device	Büchi Pure C-850 FlashPrep
Stationary phase	Type: Reversed-phase Type of Column: Gemini C18 Composition: C18 bonded silica
Column dimensions	Length and diameter: 250*50mm, 10 μ m

Mobile Phase	Composition: Solvent A: Water + 0.1% formic acid Solvent B: Acetonitrile + 0.1% formic acid pH: 2.5
Flow rate	30 ml/min
Detection	UV= 220-600 nm, 210, 254, 300, 350 nm
Total injected mass	300 mg per run

Table 7. Gradient – Fraction I separation

Gradient program	Time [min]	% Solvent A	% Solvent B
0	0	70	30
3	3	70	30
12	15	45	55
30	45	15	85
10	55	0	100
10	65	0	100

2.2.3.4 Isolation of compounds **7** and **8** from Fraction II (methanol phase)

The purification of the methanol phase, Fraction II (12.8 g), was performed using preparative HPLC according to the conditions specified in Tables 6 and 8. This resulted in the isolation of four pure compounds: compound **7** (6.9 mg, t_R = 62 min), **8** (14.2 mg, t_R = 70 min) in subfractions 10 and 13, respectively, in addition to compounds **2** (712.7 mg, t_R = 42 min) and **5** (19.9 mg, t_R = 56 min) that were re-isolated from subfractions 7 and 12.

Table 8. Gradient – Fraction II Separation

Gradient program	Time [min]	% Solvent A	% Solvent B
0	0	60	40
10	10	60	40
10	20	45	55
45	65	10	90
5	70	0	100
5	75	0	100

2.2.4 Large-scale cultivation and purification of pure compounds from *B. neobassiana*

This fungus' remarkable capacity to produce a wide variety of secondary metabolites, both previously known and uncharacterized compounds, and its extract placing in the top twenty of the antiviral screening served as the impetus for further study. Comprehensive analytical investigations were performed, revealing a substantial abundance and variety of secondary metabolites within the extract.

2.2.4.1 Large-scale fermentation

This strain was cultivated and extracted in Thailand. First, the fungus was cultured on potato dextrose agar (PDA). A seven-mm-diameter cork borer was used to carefully remove five mycelial plugs from an actively growing colony to initiate the main cultures. The plugs were then inoculated into 500 mL Erlenmeyer flasks, each containing 200 mL of potato dextrose broth (PDB) medium. For the experiment, 50 culture flasks (10 L) in total were used. The flasks were then incubated at 23 °C with agitation set to 140 rpm in the shaker. The levels of glucose in each culture broth were routinely monitored to track the development of the cultures using urine glucose test strips.

The cultures were allowed to continue growing after the glucose was depleted for an extra three days to promote the synthesis of secondary metabolites. Following this period of incubation, the cultures were harvested. The extraction procedure was performed using the same methods described in Section 2.2.2.1. The acquired total extracts—from both the mycelia and the supernatant—were brought to Germany for additional chemical and biological examination.

2.2.4.2 Isolation of compounds 9-11

The mycelial extract of *B. neobassiana* (91.1 mg) was subjected to preparative HPLC, applying conditions in Tables 9 and 10, which afforded three pure substances: **9** (1.2 mg, $t_R = 41$ min), **10** (1.2 mg, $t_R = 51$ min), and **11** (1.8 mg, $t_R = 54$ min) from fractions 10, 12/13, and 14, respectively.

Table 9. Parameter for the purification of the mycelial extract of *B. neobassiana*

Parameter	Description
HPLC-device	Gilson PLC 2250
Stationary phase	Type: Reversed-phase Type of Column: Gemini C18 Composition: C18 bonded silica
Column dimensions	Length and diameter: 250*50mm, 10 μ m
Mobile Phase	Composition: Solvent A: Water + 0.1% formic acid Solvent B: Acetonitrile + 0.1% formic acid pH: 2.5
Flow rate	45 ml/min
Detection	UV= 220-600 nm, 225, 345, 367, 350 nm
Total injected mass	91.1 mg

Table 10. Gradient – mycelial extract separation of *B. neobassiana*

Time [min]	% Solvent A	% Solvent B
0	65	35

5	65	35
50	20	80
55	0	100
60	0	100

2.2.4.3 Isolation of compounds 12-15

The purification of the supernatant extract of *B. neobassiana* (269 mg) was carried out using preparative HPLC to isolate compounds: **12** (7.5 mg, $t_R = 48$ min), **13** (1.1 mg, $t_R = 52$ min), **14** (1.5 mg, $t_R = 57$ min), **15** (4.0 mg, $t_R = 60$ min), **10** (2.5 mg, $t_R = 36$ min) and **11** (9.8 mg, $t_R = 39$ min), from fractions 10/11, 13, 14, 15/16/17, 5 and 6/7/8, respectively. The purification process involved using a flow rate of 30 ml/min, with the separation parameters detailed in Tables 9 and 11.

Table 11. Gradient – supernatant extract separation of *B. neobassiana*

Time [min]	% Solvent A	% Solvent B
0	75	25
5	75	25
15	55	45
70	0	100
80	0	100

2.2.5 Large-scale cultivation and purification of pure compounds from *S. aurantia*

Based on its performance in the antiviral screening, where it was one of the top five hit extracts, and its capacity to produce both known and unknown compounds in appreciable quantities, *S. aurantia* was chosen for further study. This promising outcome indicated the strain's potential as a valuable source of antiviral compounds.

2.2.5.1 Large-scale fermentation

The fungal strain *S. aurantia* was cultivated and extracted in Thailand. The fungus was cultivated on PDA medium. Five mycelial plugs, each with a diameter of seven mm, were aseptically removed from an actively growing colony and then inoculated with rice. Each rice culture was prepared by filling 10 different flasks with 180 g of rice and 180 mL of distilled water, then autoclaving the mixture. Then, for the following 16 days, these flasks were incubated under static conditions at room temperature. At this point, the mycelia had grown completely.

When the cultures reached the proper growth stage, extraction was performed on them. The cultures were first soaked in acetone for a whole night. The ultrasonic bath was then used to

do three rounds of extraction, with freshly added acetone for each extraction cycle. The extraction methodology employed here was carried out according to the steps described in Section 2.2.2.2.

The acquired total extracts were brought to Germany to be utilized for further chemical and biological analysis.

2.2.5.2 Vacuum Liquid Chromatography

Vacuum liquid chromatography was followed to separate the total extract of the solid rice culture of *S. aurantia* (15.0 g). The total extract was dissolved in the least amount of acetone:methanol (1:1) mixture and loaded on 15 g of silica gel that was let to dry overnight. The loaded dry silica gel was carefully dry-packed on top of a column filled with dry silica gel for vacuum liquid chromatography. The elution procedure was performed using gradient elution as explained in Table 12 to yield ten fractions of 1 L each that were collected and evaporated separately under reduced pressure until dryness.

Table 12. Gradient – Vacuum liquid chromatography of *S. aurantia*

Fraction Number	Solvent A	Solvent B	Solvent ratio (A:B)	Fraction weight (mg)
Fraction 1	Heptane	-	100%	72.2
Fraction 2	Heptane	Ethyl acetate	7:3	1,200
Fraction 3	Heptane	Ethyl acetate	3:7	1,315.7
Fraction 4	Ethyl acetate	-	100%	306.6
Fraction 5	Ethyl acetate	Methanol	9:1	1,279.9
Fraction 6	Ethyl acetate	Methanol	7:3	489.7
Fraction 7	Acetone	-	100%	32.6
Fraction 8	Methanol	Acetone	1:1	765.5
Fraction 9	Methanol	-	100%	1,011.0
Fraction 10	Methanol	0.1% Formic Acid	-	227.9

2.2.5.3 Isolation of compounds 16-18 from Fraction 4

To purify Fraction 4 (306.6 mg) with preparative HPLC, we used the same conditions as described in Tables 9 and 13. The only difference was the flow rate of 30 ml/min. Two separate runs, each using 150 mg but with different gradients, were employed.

Four distinct pure compounds were isolated: compound **16** (9.1 mg, $t_R = 67$ min), **17** (19.5 mg, $t_R = 81$ min), and **18** (2.8 mg, $t_R = 89$ min) were detected in subfractions 4.3–4.7, 4.11, and 4.13, respectively.

Table 13. Gradient – separation of Fraction 4

Time [min]	% Solvent A	% Solvent B
0	70	30
5	70	30
15	50	50

90	0	100
105	0	100

2.2.5.4 Isolation of compound **19** from Fraction **6**

In the purification process of Fraction 6 (489.7 mg) with preparative HPLC, the methods outlined in Tables 9 and 14 were employed, applying a flow rate of 20 ml/min and the Nucleodur C18 HTec column with a size of 250 × 21 mm, 10µm and an injection mass of 50 mg. As a result, two pure compounds were obtained: compound **19** (1.2 mg, $t_R = 19$ min) from subfraction 6.2 while compound **17** (2.7 mg, $t_R = 24$ min) was also purified in subfraction 6.4.

Table 14. Gradient – separation of Fraction 6

Time [min]	% Solvent A	% Solvent B
0	50	50
2	50	50
22	10	90
30	0	100
35	0	100

2.2.5.5 Isolation of compounds **20** and **21** from Fraction **8**

Preparative HPLC was applied for the purification of fraction 8 using conditions as described in Tables 12 and 15, employing a flow rate of 30 ml/min. Two runs were performed, each with an injection mass of 380 mg, resulting in the attainment of two pure compounds: **20** (4.3 mg, $t_R = 62$ min) in fraction 8.7 and **21** (21.4 mg, $t_R = 66$ min) in fraction 8.8.

Table 15. Gradient – separation of Fraction 8

Time [min]	% Solvent A	% Solvent B
0	85	15
5	85	15
15	65	35
80	0	100
90	0	100

2.2.5.6 Isolation of compound **9** from Fraction **10**

The purification process of fraction 10 was performed using preparative HPLC following the conditions specified in Tables 12 and 16, utilizing a flow rate of 30 ml/min and an injection mass of 227 mg. The purification resulted in the isolation of one pure compound, identified as compound **9** (0.5 mg, $t_R = 26$ min) in fraction 10.3.

Table 16. Gradient – separation of Fraction 10

Time [min]	% Solvent A	% Solvent B
0	70	30
5	70	30
15	50	50
45	20	80
55	0	100
65	0	100

2.2.6 Structure elucidation

The Bruker Avance III 500 (^1H : 500 MHz, ^{13}C : 125 MHz) and Bruker Avance III 700 with a 5 mm TXI cryoprobe (^1H : 700 MHz, ^{13}C : 175 MHz) spectrometers were used for the 1D and 2D NMR analyses. These analyses were carried out at the NMR facility of Helmholtz Centre for Infection Research by Esther Surges and Christel Kakoschke. The samples were dissolved in DMSO- d_6 or acetone- d_6 to facilitate the analysis. An ACQUITY UPLC® BEH C18 column (130Å, 1.7 μm , 2.1 mm \times 50 mm; Waters) was used in conjunction with an Agilent 1200 series HPLC-UV system to evaluate pure compounds (at a concentration of 1 mg/mL in acetone:methanol). This system was coupled with an Electrospray Ionization Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry (ESI-TOF-MS), operating within a scan range of 100–2500 m/z , a rate of 2 Hz, a capillary voltage of 4500 V, and a dry temperature of 200 °C using the Maxis instrument from Bruker to yield high-resolution electrospray ionization mass spectra. Structure elucidation of the isolated compounds was concluded by Prof. Sherif S. Ebada, a fellow postdoc in the department of Microbial Drugs group based on exhaustive spectral analyses including HRESIMS, 1D ($^1\text{H}/^{13}\text{C}$) and 2D (^1H - ^1H COSY, HMBC, HSQC and ROESY) NMR spectroscopy.

2.2.6.1 Mosher's analysis

A 0.5 mg of the corresponding compound was dissolved in 50 μL of pyridine- d_5 and 10 μL of (*R*)-MTPA chloride were added for the preparation of the (*R*)-MTPA ester. The mixture was incubated at room temperature for 60 minutes. Then, 3 μL of the reaction mixture was withdrawn and diluted with acetone to a final volume of 100 μL . A change in the chromatogram and the absence of the main compound peak indicated the successful formation of the ester. Pyridine- d_5 was used to further dilute the reaction solution. Similar to this, 10 μL of (*S*)-MTPA chloride was added to synthesize the (*R*)-MTPA ester. Following these reactions, 1H, COSY, and HSQC NMR spectra were obtained (Pfütze et al. 2023).

2.2.7 Tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) measurements and data analysis

Total extracts from the extraction were used to prepare samples for tandem mass spectrometry. For this, a Dionex Ultimate 3000RS system with a Kinetex C18 column (1.7 μm , 21 \times 150 mm, 100 \AA) and a 2 μL injection volume was used to analyze each sample, dissolved at a concentration of 450 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ in DMSO. The flow rate of mobile phase consisting of A (H_2O + 0.1% formic acid) and B (acetonitrile + 0.1% formic acid) was 0.3 mL/min. Over the course of 25 minutes, the gradient changed from 1% B to 100% B. UV data (190–600 nm) was collected, and MS spectra were acquired using a timsTOF Pro 2 mass spectrometer (Bruker Daltonics) with parameters: spectra rate 9.52 Hz, PASEF on, cycle time 320 ms, MS/MS scans 2, scan range (m/z 100–1800 Da). Data was acquired in positive and negative ESI modes. Using MetaboScape[®] 2022, the data was pre-processed to exclude any blank features and the remaining features based on accurate molecular weight with NPatlas databases. Compound hits were validated using MetaboScape, considering predicted molecular formulae and fragmentation patterns (Wongkanoun et al. 2023).

2.2.8 Spectral analysis of pure compounds

2.2.8.1 UV/Vis absorption

A UV-2450 UV/Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu Corporation) was used to measure the compounds' UV absorbance properties between 190 and 600 nm. The compounds were dissolved in methanol Uvasol[®] at a final concentration of 0.01–0.03 mg/mL. Two cuvettes were used in the experiment: one held 1 mL of methanol Uvasol[®] as the reference, and the other 1 mL of the respective test compound solution. Prior to measurement, baseline correction was performed, followed by auto-zeroing. To identify the compounds' absorbance maximum values within the designated wavelength range, UV absorption experiments were conducted. The extinction coefficient (ϵ) was calculated as following:

$$\epsilon = \frac{A}{c * l}$$

ϵ : molar extinction coefficient (in L/mol*cm)

A: absorbance of the sample

c: concentration of the absorbing species (in mol/L)

l: path length of the cuvette (in cm).

2.2.8.2 Circular dichroism

Using a J-815 CD spectrometer (Jasco), circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy was used to examine the compounds in methanol Uvasol[®]. The experimental procedure involved several steps. First, methanol Uvasol[®] was used as reference to get a baseline measurement. This baseline measurement encompassed the wavelength range of 190 to 500 nm and was repeated five times to ensure accuracy. The compounds were then subjected to CD measurements using the same wavelength range and repetition protocol. This approach allowed for the evaluation of the compounds' circular dichroism characteristics.

2.2.8.3 Optical rotation

Using an Anton Paar MCP 150 polarimeter (sodium D line, nickel alloy sample cell 100 mm 3 mm, 0.7 mL), the compounds' optical rotation was assessed. Prior to measurements, the polarimeter was calibrated with a quartz plate for accuracy. After calibration, the solvent used for compound dissolution, methanol Uvasol[®], was used to carry out auto-zeroing. For the majority of substances, the optical rotation values were calculated at concentrations of 1 mg/mL, whilst those with amounts less than 1 mg were tested at concentrations of 0.01 mg/mL. The specific optical rotation values were calculated employing the subsequent formula:

$$[\alpha]_D^{20} = \frac{\alpha * 100}{c * l}$$

$[\alpha]$: specific optical rotation (in °*dm³/g*cm)

T: Temperature (20°C)

D: sodium D line (589 nm)

α : observed optical rotation (in °)

c: concentration of the sample (in g/100 mL)

l: path length of the sample cell (in dm)

2.2.9 Bioactivity assays

2.2.9.1 Antiviral assay

The isolated compounds were dissolved using DMSO at a concentration of 10 mM each at a volume of 50 μ L to test their antiviral efficacy against the CHIKV. This was carried out in a 96-well sterile plate, taking into account the molecular weights of the compounds. Dr. Jackson Muema from the "Compound Profiling and Screening" group (CPRO) at the Helmholtz Centre

for Infection Research carried out the bioassays. Additionally, DMSO served as a solvent control (Xu et al. 2017).

2.2.9.2 MIC and Cytotoxicity assay

Wera Collisi performed the antimicrobial and cytotoxic activities. Prior to testing, a solution of each compound was prepared at a concentration of 1 mg/mL.

A serial dilution assay with compounds was conducted on the test organisms specified in Table 17 for antibacterial and antifungal assessments, as described by Becker et al. (2020). Furthermore, cytotoxicity experiments were carried out utilizing the cell lines listed in Table 18, as described by Harms et al. (2021).

Table 17. Microbial strains and experimental conditions employed for the antimicrobial assay

Organism	Strain number ^a	Absorbance at OD 548/600	Reference ^b	Temperature
<i>Schizosaccharomyces pombe</i>	DSM 70572	548, 0.1	2µL N	30
<i>Pichia anomala</i>	DSM 6766	548, 0.1	2µL N	30
<i>Mucor hiemalis</i>	DSM 2656	548, 0.1	2µL N	30
<i>Candida albicans</i>	DSM 1665	548, 0.1	2µL N	30
<i>Rhodotorula glutinis</i>	DSM 10134	548, 0.1	2µL N	30
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	DSM 30008	600, 0.01	2µL C	30
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	DSM 1116	600, 0.01	2µL G	37
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	DSM 10	600, 0.01	20µL O	37
<i>Mycobacterium smegmatis</i>	ATCC 700084	548, 0.1	2µL K	37
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	DSM 346	600, 0.01	2µL G	37
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	DSM PA14	548, 0.1	2µL G	37
<i>Chromobacterium violaceum</i>	DSM 30191	600, 0.01	2µL G	30

^a DSM. Leibniz-Institute DSMZ – German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH, Braunschweig, Germany; ATCC. American Type Culture Collection.

^b N: Nystatin; O: Oxytetracycline; C: Ciprofloxacin; G: Gentamycin; K: Kanamycin

Table 18. Cell lines employed for the cytotoxicity assay

Cell line	Collection number ^a	Culture media ^b
Murine fibroblast (L-929)	ACC 2	DMEM
Human HeLa servix carcinoma (KB-3-1)	ACC 158	DMEM
Human breast adenocarcinoma (MCF-7)	ACC 115	RPMI 1640
Human lung carcinoma (A549)	ACC 107	F12K

^a ACC. Leibniz-Institute DSMZ – German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH, Braunschweig, Germany

^b DMEM: Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium; MEM NEAA: Minimum Essential Medium Non-Essential Amino Acids.

2.2.9.3 Anti-biofilm assay

A protocol was followed in order to assess the anti-biofilm activity of several substances against *St. aureus* (DSM 1104) biofilms (Soliga et al. 2021). From a -20°C stock, *St. aureus* was cultivated and given an 18-hour incubation period. The culture's OD₆₀₀ was adjusted to a 0.001 McFarland standard in a medium suspension for the biofilm assay. Subsequently, the *St. aureus* biofilm was cultivated alongside serially diluted compounds (ranging from 125 to 1.9 µg/ml) for 24 hours. Using crystal violet staining and subsequent washing procedures, the compounds' inhibitory effect on the biofilm was assessed. A microtiter plate reader (Synergy 2, BioTek) was then used to measure the stained biomass. Methanol was employed as a solvent control, serving as the 100% reference with no inhibition activity against the *St. aureus* biofilm. Microporenic acid (MAA) was used as a positive control (Chepkirui et al. 2018). Each experiment was repeated twice with duplicate samples, and subsequent analyses were carried out accordingly.

3 Results

In this thesis, our analysis focused on the chemical properties of secondary metabolites derived from fungal extracts and their corresponding strains which exhibited efficacy against the CHIKV. The twenty selected extracts all shared the ability to uphold an infectivity rate below 40% while demonstrating a cell viability of over 70%. The extracts from three strains, *C. javanica*, *B. neobassiana*, and *S. aurantia*, were chosen. Those extracts were subjected to further screening and cultivation in a scaled-up setting. The aim was to explore the potential of these total extracts in a more comprehensive manner.

3.1 Results of the small-scale cultivation of *C. javanica*

In the case of *C. javanica*, the amount and variety of compounds derived were noticeably high when using the GG1-medium (around 400 mg of mycelial and supernatant extract per 200 ml

of culture). Upon successful cultivation, the secondary metabolites were isolated and purified to enable detailed chemical analysis and bioactivity assessment.

3.2 Secondary metabolites isolated from *C. javanica*

Eight compounds were successfully obtained after the scaled-up fermentation and subsequent purification of the total extract. To understand their complex structures, each of these substances underwent thorough chemical analysis utilizing LC-MS, high-resolution electrospray Ionization Mass Spectrometry (HR-ESI-MS), and NMR spectroscopy. Notably, all of these compounds belong to the beauverolide family. Within this collection, four compounds have been previously described, while the remaining four are novel. The structural elucidation and bioactivity testing are ongoing. The LC-MS-UV chromatogram shown below illustrates the total extract from Fraction II of the liquid-liquid pre-separation, visually allocating the isolated compounds.

Figure 2. LC-MS-UV chromatogram (at 190-600 nm) from Fraction II of the liquid-liquid pre-separation of *C. javanica*

3.2.1 Physicochemical characterization of compounds 1-8

Compound **1** (1.2 mg, $t_R = 9.8$ min) was dissolved in $DMSO-d_6$ to enable accurate NMR measurements. The further analysis of the observed NMR spectra, along with the HR-ESI-MS data, revealed the molecular formula $C_{21}H_{37}N_3O_5$ and identified it as beauverolide T. Continuing, compound **2** (718.0 mg, $t_R = 10.9$ min) was solubilized in $DMSO-d_6$ and identified

as beauverolide M through NMR and HR-ESI-MS analysis, with the chemical formula $C_{23}H_{41}N_3O_5$ (Kuzma et al. 2001). Notably, compound **3** (3.2 mg, $t_R= 11.8$ min) was submitted for 3D electron diffraction examination, due to solubility challenges across various solvents. The identification of compound **3**, having a molecular formula of $C_{29}H_{42}N_4O_5$, that was determined using HR-ESI-MS, led to the identification of compound **3** as beauverolide Q. Compound **4** (14.1 mg, $t_R= 11.8$ min), beauverolide I, was dissolved in $DMSO-d_6$ for NMR analysis. The NMR data was combined with the HR-ESI-MS data, which revealed its molecular formula as $C_{27}H_{41}N_3O_5$ (Kuzma et al. 2001). The solubilization of compound **5** (26.2 mg, $t_R= 13.4$ min) was conducted in a $CHCl_3$ -MeOH (4:1) mixture for NMR analysis. With the help of NMR data and the molecular formula $C_{29}H_{45}N_3O_5$ that was obtained from HR-ESI-MS analyses, compound **5** was identified as beauverolide L (Jegorov et al. 1994). Similarly, compound **6** (0.7 mg, $t_R= 13.3$ min) was measured using NMR after being dissolved in $DMSO-d_6$. This data, in combination with the molecular formula $C_{31}H_{46}N_4O_5$ resulting from HR-ESI-MS analysis, was utilized in the identification of compound **6** as beauverolide R. Compound **7** (6.9 mg, $t_R= 13.3$ min) was subjected to an NMR study using $DMSO-d_6$ as the solvent. The collective findings from NMR analysis and HR-ESI-MS data confirmed the identity of beauverolide J_B, aligned with its molecular formula of $C_{35}H_{46}N_4O_5$ (Helaly et al. 2019). Lastly, compound **8** (14.2 mg, $t_R= 14.2$ min) was dissolved in a $CHCl_3$ -MeOH mixture (4:1) for NMR measurements. The detailed NMR analysis together with the HR-ESI-MS data clarified compound **8** as a new beauverolide called beauverolide S, characterized by a molecular formula of $C_{24}H_{41}N_3O_7$.

Figure 3. Compound 1-8; the structures in blue are proposed structure, further NMR analysis are need for confirmation

3.2.2 Metabolomics insights into the structural diversity of beauverolides produced by *C. javanica*

Cordyceps javanica has been known to produce a subclass of cyclodepsipeptides termed beauverolides. These compounds typically contain one 3-hydroxy-4-methyl fatty acid, two L-amino acids, and one D-amino acid. Among these compounds, beauverolide I (**4**), with a molecular mass of 487.3043 Da, consists of phenylalanine, alanine, leucine, and a 3-hydroxy-4-methyl octanoyl residue. Through molecular networking and MS/MS fragmentation pattern analyses, a correlation has been established between beauverolide I (**4**) and beauverolide T (**1**), a novel compound with a neutral mass of 411.2736 Da. The difference of 76 Da between the two compounds indicates the loss of a C₆H₈ group from beauverolide I (**4**) to produce beauverolide T (**1**). This shift represents the loss of a phenyl group, leading to the composition of beauverolide T (**1**) of two alanines, one leucine, and 3-hydroxy-4-methyloctanoic acid. beauverolide T (**1**) is also related to beauverolide M (**2**), distinguished by a molecular weight of 439.3047 Da and consisting of alanine, valine, leucine, and a 3-hydroxy-4-methyl octanoyl residue. The 28 Da difference in molecular weight, which is structurally speaking C₂H₄, suggests an alanine-valine exchange of beauverolide T (**1**) to yield beauverolide M (**2**), confirming the composition of beauverolide T (**1**) as previously described. Beauverolide M (**2**) is connected with beauverolide I (**4**), differing by 48 Da, indicating a C₄ modification attributed to the replacement of valine in beauverolide M (**2**) with phenylalanine in beauverolide I (**4**).

Beauverolide M (**2**) is further interrelated with beauverolide L (**5**), with a molecular weight of 515.3359 Da. The 76 Da difference between the two compounds can be associated with the substitution of valine with phenylalanine and the elongation of the fatty acid chain by an ethyl group. This structural transformation can be illustrated by the introduction of a phenyl group, which results in the loss of two methyl groups. Therefore, beauverolide L (**5**) encompasses leucine, alanine, phenylalanine, and a 3-hydroxy-4-methyl decanoyl residue.

Furthermore, this compound is connected with beauverolide J_b (**7**), with a molecular weight of 602.3468 Da. The correlation between those two compounds is characterized by a mass difference of 87 Da and, therefore, CH₄N₂O₂. This structural shift is caused by a phenylalanine-to-tryptophan substitution and an alanine-to-phenylalanine substitution.

Beauverolide J_b (**7**) shares a close linkage with beauverolide Q (**3**), which has a molecular mass of 526.3151 Da. The connection between beauverolide J_b (**7**) and beauverolide Q (**3**) is marked

by a loss of 76 Da, indicating a phenylalanine-to-alanine substitution, similar to the correlation detected between beauverolide M (**2**) and beauverolide L (**5**). The 28 Da disparity between beauverolide Q (**3**) and beauverolide R (**6**), with a neutral mass of 554.3469 Da, is paralleled by the structural change between beauverolide T (**1**) and beauverolide M (**2**). This involves the exclusion of a C₂H₄ unit from beauverolide R (**6**) to generate beauverolide Q (**3**). This structural variation arises from the use of different 3-hydroxy-4-methyl fatty acids during biosynthesis. Beauverolide R (**6**) encompasses a 3-hydroxy-4-methyl decanoyl residue, while beauverolide Q (**3**) features a 3-hydroxy-4-methyl octanoyl residue. Since beauverolide R (**6**) awaits comprehensive structural elucidation, its correlation in the molecular network helps to confirm its hypothetical structure approach, encompassing tryptophan, alanine, and leucine. Thereby, beauverolide Q (**3**) comprises tryptophan, alanine, leucine, and a 3-hydroxy-4-methyl decanoyl residue.

After a comprehensive data analysis and examination of the molecular network, additional annotations became visible. By comparing the masses with existing literature in terms of m/z values and molecular formulas, it was possible to identify further beauverolides present in the total extract. Through this comparative approach, the presence of compounds was confirmed, although their isolation was not possible under the conditions used. The complex network interactions and relationships among these features significantly helped in the accurate assignment of these beauverolides. The comprehensive outcomes of this systematic evaluation are presented in Table 19.

Table 19. Dereplicated beauverolides from *C. javanica* total extract

Compound	Molecular weight [Da]	Molecular formula
Beauverolide B	543.3671	C ₃₁ H ₄₉ N ₃ O ₅
Beauverolide C	591.3670	C ₃₅ H ₄₉ N ₃ O ₅
Beauverolide D	501.3204	C ₂₈ H ₄₃ N ₃ O ₅
Beauverolide F	563.3356	C ₃₃ H ₄₅ N ₃ O ₅
Beauverolide K	630.3778	C ₃₇ H ₅₀ N ₄ O ₅
Beauverolide N	503.2996	C ₂₇ H ₄₁ N ₃ O ₆
Beauverolide P	467.3361	C ₂₅ H ₄₅ N ₃ O ₅

In addition, a compound displaying a molecular weight of 515.3358 Da (t_R = 17.2 minutes) was detected. This compound is distinct from beauverolide L (**5**), which eluted at 16.6 minutes.

Beauverolide M (**2**): White powder; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 440.3126 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 462.2937 $[M+Na]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 879.6172 $[2M+H]^+$ (calculated for $C_{23}H_{42}N_3O_5$; m/z 440.3119)

Beauverolide Q (**3**): White powder; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 527.3226 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 549.3046 $[M+Na]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 1053.6379 $[2M+H]^+$ (calculated for $C_{29}H_{43}N_4O_5$; m/z 527.3228)

Beauverolide I (**4**): White powder; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 488.3123 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 510.2939 $[M+Na]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 975.6166 $[2M+H]^+$ (calculated for $C_{27}H_{42}N_3O_5$; m/z 488.3119)

Beauverolide L (**5**): White powder; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 516.3437 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 538.3251 $[M+Na]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 1031.6789 $[2M-H]^-$ (calculated for $C_{29}H_{46}N_3O_5$; m/z 516.3432)

Beauverolide R (**6**): White powder; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 555.354 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 577.3359 $[M+Na]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 1109.7009 $[2M-H]^+$ (calculated for $C_{31}H_{47}N_4O_5$; m/z 555.3541)

Beauverolide J_b (**7**): White powder; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 603.3555 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 625.3372 $[M+Na]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 1205.7031 $[2M+H]^+$ (calculated for $C_{35}H_{47}N_4O_5$; m/z 603.3541)

Beauverolide S (**8**): Colorless oily; UV/Vis (MeOH) λ_{max} ($\log \epsilon$): 274 nm (4.24) and 200 nm (4.07); HR-ESI-MS: m/z 484.3068 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 506.2884 $[M+Na]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 965.5901 $[2M-H]^-$ (calculated for $C_{24}H_{42}N_3O_7$; m/z 484.3017)

3.3 Secondary metabolites isolated from *B. neobassiana*

Seven different secondary metabolites were successfully isolated during the scale-up fermentation and subsequent purification of the obtained total extracts. To elucidate their structures, each of these compounds underwent chemical analysis using a combination of LC-MS, HR-ESI-MS, and NMR spectroscopy. It's worth highlighting that all of these compounds are tenellins, two of which are novel entities. Bioactivity testing and structural elucidation are continuing. The LC-MS-UV chromatograms provided visualize the composition of the total extracts, illustrating the distribution of the isolated compounds.

Figure 5. LC-MS-UV chromatogram (at 190-600 nm) from supernatant extract of *B. neobassiana*

Figure 6. LC-MS-UV chromatogram (at 190-600 nm) from mycelial extract of *B. neobassiana*.

3.3.1 Physicochemical characterization compounds 9-15

Figure 7. Chemical structures of compounds **9-15**

Compound **9** (1.7 mg, $t_R = 5.0$ min) was dissolved in acetone- d_6 and submitted for NMR measurements. The data obtained from these measurements, together with the molecular formula $C_{12}H_9NO_6$ obtained from HR-ESI-MS analysis, aided in the identification of this compound as vancouverone C. Subsequently, compound **10** (3.7 mg, $t_R = 8.4$ min) was solubilized in acetone- d_6 to enable NMR measurements. The thorough NMR investigation was corroborated by HR-ESI-MS data, which concurred with its molecular formula $C_{21}H_{23}NO_5$. Compound **10** was characterized as pyridovericin (Takahashi et al. 1998).

Likewise, compound **11** (11.6 mg, $t_R = 8.7$ min) was dissolved in acetone- d_6 to conduct NMR analysis. This extensive analysis, in combination with HR-ESI-MS measurements, which disclosed a molecular formula of $C_{21}H_{23}NO_6$, confirmed compound **11** structural identity as 15-hydroxytenellin (Halo et al. 2008). To enable NMR measurements, the dissolution of compound **12** (7.5 mg, $t_R = 10.4$ minutes) in DMSO- d_6 was performed. The comprehensive NMR investigation and the HR-ESI-MS analysis yielding its molecular formula as $C_{21}H_{25}NO_5$ established compound **12** as prototenellin D (Halo et al. 2008).

Compound **13** (1.1 mg, $t_R = 10.7$ min) was solubilized in DMSO- d_6 for NMR measurements. The comprehensive NMR analysis verified by HR-ESI-MS, which revealed its molecular formula as $C_{21}H_{23}NO_5$, classified compound **13** structural identity as vancouverone D.

Similarly, compound **14** (1.5 mg, $t_R = 11.7$ min) was dissolved in DMSO- d_6 for the facilitation of NMR measurements. Through examination of the acquired NMR spectra, coupled with HR-ESI-MS data yielding a molecular formula of $C_{21}H_{23}NO_4$, the identification of compound **14** as pretenellin B was achieved (Halo et al. 2008).

Lastly, compound **15** (4.0 mg, $t_R = 12.1$ min) underwent dissolution in DMSO- d_6 , thereby enabling NMR measurements. The comprehensive analysis of the resulting NMR spectra, complemented by HR-ESI-MS data revealing a molecular formula of $C_{21}H_{23}NO_5$, confirmed compound **15** identity as tenellin (Halo et al. 2008).

3.3.2 Bioactivity of *B. neobassiana* metabolites

3.3.2.1 Antiviral activity

To carry out the antiviral study, all seven isolated compounds were brought to a concentration of 10 mM. However, none of the examined compounds showed any detectable antiviral activity against CHIKV.

3.3.2.2 Cytotoxic activity

Table 20. Cytotoxic activity of compounds 9-15

Compound	L929 with IC ₅₀ [mM]	KB3.3 with IC ₅₀ [mM]	A549 with IC ₅₀ [mM]	MCF-7 with IC ₅₀ [mM]
15-Hydroxytenellin (11)	6.75	6.0	8.1	2.6
Prototenellin D (12)	70.1	64.7	NT	NT
Pretenellin B (14)	48.2	20.2	NT	NT
Tenellin (15)	0.79	0.79	2.0	0.24
Control Epo B	$2.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$7.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$7.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$7.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$

NT: not tested

Tenellin (**15**) demonstrated the most significant cytotoxic activity among the assessed compounds in this cohort. However, when tested against the MCF-7 cell line. Moreover, this compound displayed considerable cytotoxic effects across the other three tested cell lines. In contrast, prototenellin D (**12**) displayed the lowest cytotoxicity when tested against L929 and KB3.3 cell lines. All four cell lines exposed to 15-hydroxytenellin (**11**) showed cytotoxicity. However, the effect is minimal. Similarly, pretenellin B (**14**) exhibited quite minimal toxicity across the panel of tested cell lines

However, due to the limited availability of the compounds and the need for additional investigations, the results of the cytotoxic and antimicrobial bioassays are still awaited.

3.3.2.3 Antimicrobial activity

Table 21. Antimicrobial activity of compounds 9-15

Organism	11 MIC µg/ml	12 MIC µg/ml	14 MIC µg/ml	15 MIC µg/ml	Reference	Inhibition (µg/mL)
<i>S.pombe</i>	n.i	n.i	NT	66.6	20µl N	4.2
<i>P. anomala</i>	n.i	n.i	NT	n.i	20µl N	16.6
<i>M. hiemalis</i>	n.i	n.i	n.i	66.6	20µl N	4.2
<i>C. albicans</i>	n.i	n.i	n.i	66.6	20µl N	8.3
<i>R. glutinis</i>	n.i	n.i	NT	n.i	20µl N	4.2
<i>A. baumannii</i>	n.i	n.i	NT	n.i	2µl C	0.52
<i>E.coli</i>	n.i	n.i	n.i	n.i	2µl G	0.83
<i>Ba. subtilis</i>	66.6	n.i	66.6	8.3	20µl O	16.6
<i>M. smegmatis</i> *	n.i	n.i	n.i	n.i	2µl K	1.7
<i>S.aureus</i>	66.6	n.i	66.6	16.6	2µl G	0.83
<i>P. aeruginosa</i> *	n.i	n.i	n.i	n.i	2µl G	0.21
<i>C. violaceum</i>	n.i	n.i	n.i	n.i	2µl G	1.67

n.i.: not identified

N: Nystatin; O: Oxytetracycline; C: Ciprobay; G: Gentamycin; K: Kanamycin

The antimicrobial activity of selected *B. neobassiana* metabolites against various bacterial and fungal strains was examined (Table 21). Except for tenellin (**15**), the majority of the tested compounds had only limited inhibitory effects on the listed microorganisms in the tested concentrations. Remarkably, tenellin (**15**) exhibited moderate activity against *Ba. subtilis*, with a MIC value of 8.3 µg/ml, which was half the value of the positive control (16.6 µg/ml). Tenellin (**15**) also showed very slight activity against *S. pombe*, *M. hiemalis*, *C. albicans*, and *St. aureus*. However, when compared to the positive control, the observed activities were not substantially remarkable. Pretenellin B (**14**) and 15-hydroxytenellin (**11**) exhibited similar patterns of growth inhibition against *St. aureus* and *Ba. subtilis*, with an MIC value of 66.6 µg/ml. However, compared to the positive control, this level of inhibition was not substantial. Despite the illustrated moderate efficacy of tenellin (**15**) against *Ba. subtilis*, it displayed limited antimicrobial potential and may not be suitable for future applications.

Nonetheless, the current status of the antibacterial and cytotoxic bioassays is pending due to the limited availability of the remaining compounds and the need for additional testing.

3.3.2.4 Anti-biofilm activity

Table 22. Anti-biofilm activity of compounds 9-15

Compound	Biofilm inhibition [% ± SD]	Potency of biofilm Inhibition ¹
Vancouverone C (9)	74 ± 4 (125 µg/ml) 63 ± 16 (62.5 µg/ml) 46 ± 9 (31.25 µg/ml) 22 ± 17 (15.62 µg/ml)	-
Pyridovericin (10)	64 ± 14 (125 µg/ml)	-

	48 ± 5 (62.5 µg/ml)	
15-OH-Tenellin (11)	86 ± 0.5 (125 µg/ml) 85 ± 2 (62.5 µg/ml) 78 ± 5 (31.25 µg/ml) 47 ± 12 (15.62 µg/ml) 15 ± 11 (7.8 µg/ml)	+
Prototenellin D (12)	84 ± 1 (125 µg/ml) 85 ± 1 (62.5 µg/ml) 80 ± 10 (31.25 µg/ml) 56 ± 8 (15.62 µg/ml) 53 ± 7 (7.8 µg/ml)	++
Vancouverone D (13)	85 ± 3 (125 µg/ml) 72 ± 3 (62.5 µg/ml) 61 ± 2 (31.25 µg/ml) 47 ± 7 (15.62 µg/ml) 34 ± 6 (7.8 µg/ml)	++
Pretenellin B (14)	83 ± 5 (125 µg/ml) 83 ± 6 (62.5 µg/ml) 79 ± 8 (31.25 µg/ml) 52 ± 6 (15.62 µg/ml) 37 ± 7 (7.8 µg/ml)	++
Tenellin (15)	78 ± 5 (125 µg/ml) 80 ± 4 (62.5 µg/ml) 73 ± 15 (31.25 µg/ml) 51 ± 19 (15.62 µg/ml) 36 ± 13 (7.8 µg/ml)	++

¹ +++ At or Below 5 µg/ml with at least 40% inhibition: activity is promising; ++ 20-30% inhibition at 5 µg/ml or around 30 % inhibition at 7.8 µg/ml below is moderate activity; + above 40% inhibition at 15.62 µg/ml: slight active; - : no activity

In the context of inhibition of biofilm formation, the examination produced notable results. A variety of inhibitory efficacies on biofilm formation were detected among the tested compounds, with prototenellin D (**12**) exhibiting the most promising activity and pyridovericin (**10**) displaying the least inhibition, resulting in no discernible impact. Vancouverone D (**13**), pretenellin B (**14**), and tenellin (**15**) showed moderate levels of biofilm inhibition with similar inhibitory values. 15-hydroxyTenellin (**11**) demonstrated slightly discernible anti-biofilm activity, while pyridovericin (**9**) showed low activity and was the second least effective in terms of inhibition. However, the observed effects in the bioassay exhibit a direct correlation with the concentration. As concentration rises, so does activity.

Figure 8. Effects on the biofilm formation of *St. aureus* after 24 h treatment with compounds. Microporenic acid A (MAA) was used as positive control. Methanol was used as solvent control and taken as 100%. Error bars indicate standard deviation of duplicates in two biological repeats.

3.3.3 Spectral data of compounds 9-15

Vancouverone C **9**: Yellow solid; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -1° (c 0.01, MeOH); UV/Vis (MeOH) λ_{\max} (log ϵ) 332 nm (3.86), 249 nm (4.40) and 200 nm (4.58); HR-ESI-MS: m/z 264.0499 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 246.0393 $[M-H_2O+H]^+$ (calculated for $C_{12}H_{10}NO_6$; m/z 264.0503)

Pyridovericin **10**: Yellow oily; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 370.1648 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 354.1697 $[M-H_2O+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 392.1467 $[M+Na]^+$ (calculated for $C_{21}H_{24}NO_5$; m/z 354.1649)

15-OH-Tenellin **11**: Yellow solid; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 386.1599 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 408.1416 $[M+Na]^+$ (calculated for $C_{21}H_{24}NO_6$; m/z 386.1598)

Prototenellin D **12**: Yellow solid; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 372.1806 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 394.1627 $[M+Na]^+$ 354.1706 $[M-H_2O+H]^+$ (calculated for $C_{21}H_{26}NO_5$; m/z 372.1805)

Vancouverone D **13**: Yellow solid; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 354.1704 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 389.1941 $[M-H_2O+H]^+$ (calculated for $C_{21}H_{24}NO_5$; m/z 354.1700)

Pretenellin B **14**: Yellow powder; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 354.17 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 376.1521 $[M+Na]^+$ (calculated for $C_{21}H_{24}NO_4$; m/z 354.17)

Tenellin **15**: Yellow powder; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 370.165 [M+H]⁺; HR-ESI-MS m/z 392.1475 [M+Na]⁺ (calculated for C₂₁H₂₄NO₅; m/z 370.1649)

3.4 Secondary metabolites isolated from *S. aurantia*

Following the scale-up fermentation and subsequent purification of the resulting total extracts, six distinct secondary metabolites were successfully isolated. Each of these substances was chemically analyzed using a combination of LC-MS, HR-ESI-MS, and NMR spectroscopy to determine their structures. Farinosones, beauvericins, and one simplicilliumtide have been discovered to be produced by this fungus. One of the six secondary metabolites are new. Testing for bioactivity and structural elucidation is ongoing. The LC-MS-UV chromatogram supplied illustrates the distribution of the isolated compounds by visualizing the composition of the entire extract before the vacuum liquid chromatography.

Figure 9. LC-MS-UV chromatogram (at 190-600 nm) from the total extract of *S. aurantia*

3.4.1 Physicochemical characterization compounds 16-21

Figure 10. Chemical structures of compounds **16-21**

In the context of our research, compound **16** (9.1 mg, $t_R = 12.9$ min), was dissolved in DMSO- d_6 for the purpose of NMR investigations. A comprehensive evaluation of the derived NMR spectra and HR-ESI-MS data, revealing the molecular formula of $C_{25}H_{29}NO_5$, endorsed the identification of compound **16** as farinosone D. Moving forward, compound **17** (22.2 mg, $t_R = 14.2$ min), underwent solubilization in DMSO- d_6 to facilitate NMR measurements. The detailed analysis of the resulting NMR spectra, coupled with HR-ESI-MS data unveiling a molecular formula of $C_{25}H_{27}NO_5$, verified compound **17** identity as farinosone B (Cheng et al. 2004).

The NMR exploration of compound **18** (2.8 mg, $t_R = 16.0$ min) was undertaken by solubilization in DMSO- d_6 to conduct NMR investigations. A comprehensive examination of the acquired NMR spectra, complemented by HR-ESI-MS data yielding the molecular formula $C_{47}H_{61}N_3O_9$, confirmed the identity of compound **18** as beauvericin B (Nilanonta et al. 2002).

Compound **19** (1.2 mg, $t_R = 12.8$ min) was examined through NMR measurements after being dissolved in Acetone- d_6 . Thorough analysis of the NMR spectra and HR-ESI-MS data aided in identifying compound **19** as farinosone A, demonstrated by a molecular formula of $C_{25}H_{27}NO_4$ (Cheng et al. 2004). Introducing compound **20** (4.3 mg, $t_R = 12.6$ min), an unreported compound, was dissolved in DMSO- d_6 for NMR investigations. Comprehensive analysis of the NMR data, coupled with HR-ESI-MS displaying a molecular formula of $C_{25}H_{39}N_3O_6$, led to the identification of compound **20** as simplicilliumtide E (Liang et al. 2016).

Compound **21** (21.4 mg, $t_R = 15.6$ min) was subjected to solubilization in DMSO- d_6 for NMR examinations. Through evaluation of the NMR spectra and HR-ESI-MS data, which indicated a molecular formula of $C_{46}H_{59}N_3O_9$, compound **21** was established to be beauvericin A (Nilanonta et al. 2002).

3.4.2 Spectral data of compounds 16-22

Farinosone D **16**: Yellow powder; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 424.2126 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 446.1947 $[M+Na]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 406.2020 $[M-H_2O+H]^+$ (calculated for $C_{25}H_{30}NO_5$; m/z 424.2118)

Farinosone B **17**: Yellow powder; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 422.1974 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 444.1797 $[M+Na]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 404.1855 $[M-H_2O+H]^+$ (calculated for $C_{25}H_{28}NO_5$; m/z 422.1962)

Beauvericin B **18**: Yellow powder; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 812.4489 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 834.4301 $[M+Na]^+$ (calculated for $C_{47}H_{62}N_3O_9$; m/z 812.4481)

Farinosone A **19**: Yellow powder; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 406.2013 $[M+H]^+$ (calculated for $C_{25}H_{28}NO_4$; m/z 406.2026)

Simpliciumtide E **20**: Brown oily; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 478.2930 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 500.2750 $[M+Na]^+$ (calculated for $C_{25}H_{40}N_3O_6$; m/z 478.2912)

Beauvericin A **21**: Orange solid; HR-ESI-MS: m/z 798.4324 $[M+H]^+$; HR-ESI-MS m/z 820.4142 $[M+Na]^+$ (calculated for $C_{46}H_{60}N_3O_9$; m/z 798.4364)

4 Discussion

The different fungi herein investigated were prioritized based on their performance against CHIKV in the medium-throughput screening phase. Because comprehensive antiviral assay results for the extracts were unavailable, which would have aided in selecting specific extracts and optimizing conditions based on the medium used, finding an antiviral compound was not successful. Nevertheless, the investigation enabled us to take a deeper look into the secondary metabolites of the three strains and their bioactivity beyond their antiviral properties.

All three strains (*C. javanica*, *B. neobassiana*, and *S. aurantia*) belong to the Cordycipitaceae family (Hypocreales, Ascomycota), a taxonomic group renowned for its entomopathogenic lifestyle (Helaly et al. 2019; Kobmoo et al. 2021; Mongkolsamrit et al. 2018). Because of their wide range of applications, expanding our understanding of entomopathogenic fungi and their

secondary metabolites holds considerable significance. They are ecologically important because they play a key role in natural environments as biocontrol agents against insects. Their secondary metabolites demonstrate a wide range of bioactivities. Understanding the complicated biosynthetic processes that lead to the development of these metabolites provides insights into the molecular mechanisms that underpin their formation. Therefore, we studied the secondary metabolite production of these fungi under different cultivation conditions and systematically characterized their structural diversity and their respective biological activities.

When utilizing GG1-medium as a cultivation medium for *C. javanica*, a significant improvement was found not only in terms of yield but also in the diversity of produced compounds. This enhancement resulted in a more noticeable accumulation of beauverolides. Beauverolides are structurally diverse, as indicated by the distinct members identified in our study—beauverolides T (1), M (2), Q (3), I (4), L (5), R (6), J_b (7), and S (8). Some of these compounds were found to be identical to those previously reported by Helaly et al. in 2019. Notably, we successfully isolated beauverolides I (4) and J_b (7) from the GG1-extract, which is consistent with the findings of Helaly et al. 2019, while they isolated beauverolides N, I (4), and J_b (7) from the same strain grown in liquid YM medium. Altogether, our study confirmed the presence of four known beauverolides—M (2), I (4), L (5) and J_b (7)—as well as four novel compounds: beauverolides T (1), Q (3), R (6), and S (8). Furthermore, our metabolomics investigation revealed the existence of beauverolides B, C, D, F, K, N, and P in the entire extract, despite the fact that isolation was not possible under the conditions used. Importantly, while Helaly et al. 2019 isolated glycoasperfuran from their extracts, our experiment did not yield this molecule.

The diverse attributes of beauverolides attract our interest, particularly their various bioactive capacities. The primary demonstrated activity of beauverolides lies in their insecticidal potential, notably with regard to the application of *B. bassiana*, from which the majority of these compounds were originally acquired (Wang et al. 2018; Wang et al. 2021). Among them, beauverolides B, C, D, and F that were detected in our total extract are reported to have such activity (Wang et al. 2018). Furthermore, numerous beauverolides—C, F, I (4), Ja, L (5), M (2), and N—have been investigated as possible calmodulin (CaM) inhibitors (Madariaga-Mazón et al. 2015), as well as having immune-modulating abilities. They have also been identified as antimicrobial agents, with beauverolide N exhibiting weak antibiofilm activity against *St. aureus* and moderate cytotoxicity against KB3.1 cells and beauverolide I (4) exhibiting slight suppression of KB3.1 cell line proliferation (Helaly et al. 2019). The

multiple properties of this compound class position them as intriguing agents with uses beyond infectious illnesses.

The biosynthesis of beauverolides requires the involvement of a conserved biosynthetic gene cluster (BGC) composed of four genes: *besA*, *besB*, *besC*, and *besD*. Three entomopathogenic fungi share these genetic elements: *B. bassiana*, *B. brongniartii*, and *C. militaris*. The *besA* gene encodes a polyketide synthase (PKS) that produces 3-hydroxy fatty acids with variable chain lengths. The *besB*, *besC*, and *besD* genes, on the other hand, encode nonribosomal peptide synthetases (NRPS) responsible for amino acid residue incorporation. This synchronized combination results in the formation of a 3-hydroxy fatty acid, two L-type amino acid residues, and one D-type amino acid residue, yielding a variety of beauverolide analogs (Yin et al. 2020). Those complex processes explain the structural diversity of this compound class.

Despite the fact that the four above-mentioned genes are likely to be found in *B. neobassiana*, a closely related fungus to *B. bassiana*, no beauverolides have been isolated from this strain. The compounds identified in the present study are from the tenellin family. This class of compounds contains a diverse set of members, seven of which have been successfully isolated, including two novel compounds. Their conserved biosynthesis begins with pretenellin A, which is essential in the synthesis of both tenellin (**15**) and hydroxytenellin (**11**), which is regulated by distinct oxidative enzymes. Significantly, pyridovericin (**10**) production begins with pretenellin B (**14**) oxidation. ORF1 encodes the cytochrome P450 oxidase, which performs the critical oxidative ring expansion, converting pretenellin A into pretenellin B (**14**), tenellin (**15**), and their derivatives. ORF2 encodes the cytochrome P450 oxidase, which facilitates the N-hydroxylation of pyridones. Pretenellin A and prototenellin D (**12**), in particular, differ from the usual 2-pyridone structure observed in other compounds in this class (Halo et al. 2008). This structural difference may have contributed to the observed notable anti-biofilm activity, with prototenellin D (**12**) exhibiting the highest activity among the investigated substances. Vancouverone D (**13**), pretenellin B (**14**) and tenellin (**15**) are the second-most active compounds in terms of biofilm inhibition. This observation emphasizes the beneficial influence of a tetramic acid ring, favoring it over the 2-pyridone motif. Surprisingly, nitrogen hydroxylation within the 2-pyridone ring has little effect on the reported activity. However, hydroxylation at C-15 in the side chain has a negative effect on activity. The absence of inhibitory activity is caused by both the presence of hydroxylation at C-15 and the absence of the hydroxyl group on N-1. Notably, prototenellin D (**12**) emerges as a viable anti-biofilm

candidate with low cytotoxicity and antimicrobial activity—a well-suited profile for possible anti-biofilm applications against *St. aureus*-biofilm. Similarly, one of the compounds examined, tenellin (**15**), shows promise against *Ba. subtilis*, a gram-positive bacterium, with a lower MIC than the positive control, gentamycin. This suggests that it may be effective against this bacterial strain.

Although tenellin (**15**) has been shown to be insecticidal (Wang et al. 2021), the reported bioactivity of its derivatives in the available literature is restricted, emphasizing the significance of this study's findings. This contribution throws light on these derivatives' potential bioactivities against bacterial infections. In close association with tenellin derivatives are the farinosones, identified in *S. aurantia*, yielding one new compounds. Farinosone A (**19**), with its claimed neurotrophic behavior, stands up for further exploration in neurodegenerative illnesses. Farinosone B (**17**), on the other hand, showed no signs of neurotrophic activity in assays (Cheng et al. 2004). Further research is needed, notably on the newly discovered farinosone D (**16**), which has a tetramic acid ring similar to prototenellin D and might exhibit anti-biofilm characteristics.

Furthermore, the beauvericins—a cyclodepsipeptide group similar to beauverolides—are among the secondary metabolites produced by *S. aurantia*. Two members of this group were isolated: beauvericin A (**21**) and B (**18**). Beauvericin is an ionophoric cyclodepsipeptide known to form cation complexes, enhancing biological membrane permeability. It is well known for its cytotoxic, apoptotic, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, insecticidal, antiviral, and nematocidal properties. Its numerous properties merit further investigation, not just in infectious disorders but also in broader applications such as the medicinal and pesticidal sectors. It lacks selectivity between gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, and it is able to inhibit cancer cell proliferation, induce apoptosis, and exhibit promising antibacterial capabilities (Wang and Xu 2012). Simplicilliumtide E (**20**), a linear peptide, has been reported to be inactive against both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. Additionally, it has exhibited limited cytotoxicity against the K562 cell line (Liang et al. 2016). Further research regarding its cytotoxicity and investigation of possible antifungal activity could be useful in developing a full understanding of its biological activity, particularly in contrast to the structurally similar and physiologically diverse beauvericin, which might contribute in achieving selectivity. Given this molecular similarity, more research is needed to explain the biosynthesis pathway of simplicilliumtide E (**20**). Still, knowledge about the secondary metabolites produced by species belonging to this genus is scarce because the genus has been

recently described. As a result, more investigation was required to identify the secondary metabolites produced by this fungus.

5 Conclusion and outlook

In conclusion, this study investigated the structural diversity and potential bioactivities of secondary metabolites produced by *C. javanica*, *B. neobassiana*, and *S. aurantia*. Despite the results from the pre-screening assessments, the complete dataset of the total extracts was not provided, and the isolated compounds had limited antiviral efficacy against CHIKV. This result, however, does not reduce the importance of the compounds' diversity and potential applications.

The compounds found in *C. javanica* were cyclodepsipeptides called beauverolides. They have a wide range of bioactivities that extend beyond their traditional insecticidal use, including cytotoxicity, immunomodulation, and anti-biofilm activities, implying their potential as adaptive agents (Helaly et al. 2019). This diverse set of bioactivities exemplifies the complex relationship between structure and function within the beauverolide family. Metabolomics investigations revealed the structural variety of these compounds and gave an example of how thorough MS/MS analysis helps in establishing structural identities, laying the framework for future research. This combination of structural knowledge, diverse bioactivity, and in-depth metabolomic insights underlines the importance of beauverolides as an interesting compound class for thorough investigation in various scientific areas.

Prototenellin D (**12**), one of the identified compounds from *B. neobassiana*, stands out as a promising candidate for anti-biofilm applications. It has limited cytotoxicity as well as minimal antibacterial activity, making it an attractive option for further research. The evaluation of seven tested compounds, two of which were novel, provided the chance to investigate the structure-activity relationship within this compound class, specifically the anti-biofilm activity against *St. aureus*-biofilms. This investigation allows for the formulation of hypotheses about the structural features that contribute to biofilm activity, which will benefit future compound optimization campaigns. Furthermore, tenellin (**15**) showed moderate activity against *Ba. subtilis*, with a lower MIC than the positive control gentamycin, indicating its efficiency against this bacterium. This study adds an important aspect to the known insecticidal properties of this compound class. Exploration of this recently described species offers the discovery of novel derivatives, thereby improving our understanding of secondary metabolites within this genus.

The study of another recently described species, *S. aurantia*, has been important in discovering its distinctive secondary metabolites since it belongs to a recently described genus. The identification of these compounds, such as farinosone A (**19**), which has shown neurotrophic effects (Cheng et al. 2004), highlights the strain's potential medicinal relevance. Further research into the bioactivities of these compounds, particularly the newly isolated farinosone D (**16**) with possible anti-biofilm action, can be interesting for future research. Furthermore, the discovery of beauvericins within this strain, compounds with diverse activity (Wang and Xu 2012), opens the door to further investigation, particularly in terms of their possible efficacy against SARS-CoV-2. However, the BGCs from farinosones and beauvericins share ancestral origin with the ones from *B. neobassiana* and *C. javanica* (Rokas et al. 2020). Also further studies regarding the biosynthetic relationship between simplicilliumtide E (**20**) and beauvericin need to be done.

Although the strains did not show significant antiviral efficacy against CHIKV, their broad potential in domains such as insecticidal, antibacterial, neurotrophic, and immunomodulatory activities opens up possibilities for a variety of applications. The discovery of eight novel compounds expands existing compound classes while emphasizing structural diversity. This requires additional research into the compounds' biological activities and their implications in a variety of sectors.

The primary goal of this thesis was to investigate the potential of secondary metabolites from invertebrate-associated fungi in Thailand for treating infectious diseases. The study emphasizes the importance of these fungi in natural product chemistry and drug discovery by investigating taxonomic linkages and metabolite correlations. Finally, this study sheds light on the diverse potential of many compounds. These discoveries add to our understanding of natural product diversity and pave the path for future research into their wide applicability in a variety of settings.

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